

COMPUTER VISION-BASED ALGORITHMS FOR RECOGNITION OF CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The construction industry generates a significant amount of waste, posing challenges for efficient waste management and resource recovery. This paper presents a preliminary study on the use of lightweight computer vision (CV) algorithms for the automatic recognition of construction and demolition waste (CDW) materials. Utilizing image datasets acquired by drones, the study aims to develop strategies for distinguishing between individual CDW materials based on the mean intensity gradient, brightness, and relative representation of color channels. Results indicate that the proposed method can effectively recognize crucial CDW materials, paving the way for potential applications in industry and geodesy. Further research is needed to test additional materials and metrics to refine the method for practical implementation.

Keywords: Computer vision, Construction and demolition waste, Classification, Recycling

1 INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is the main consumer of mineral and other non-renewable resources in the EU and according to the Eurostat reports it produces about 35% of the total waste and more than all other wastes combined if displaced soil is excluded from the list [1, 2]. Most of this waste is produced during the construction and demolition stages. Although there have been several initiatives to tackle issues of construction and demolition waste (CDW), landfilling or downcycling of CDW is still prevalent [3]. There are two broad reasons for the current unsatisfactory situation regarding CDW: low rates of recovery in a few EU countries and low value of reused or recycled materials/products. There is generally a lack of confidence among end customers in the quality of recycled CDW due to improper sorting and contamination and low control over the material quality and homogeneity [4]. First, the volume of materials entering the CDW stream must be minimized, and, secondly, CDW must be treated and better controlled to provide materials for the reuse of high-value products, with traceability and quality assurance. The solutions that enable achieving these goals must be easily adoptable by all stakeholders involved in the processes of CDW generation and management to reach the expected future EU target of high CDW recovery and most importantly the status of zero CDW by 2050.

According to the Ministry of the Environment (ME), there are over 230 CDW stationary sorting plants and 83 mobile sorters in the Czech Republic alone, capable of processing 12 Mt annually. However, it is reported by the ME that less than 1% has been used as secondary material. Unreliable and expensive sorting results in poor quality of the recycled material and traditionally, this material is commonly used as a backfill material. This way, huge amounts of CDW materials are devaluated, and non-renewable natural resources (sand, gravel) are needlessly depleted. Based on their recycling or contamination potential, it makes sense to distinguish (and separate) the following CDW materials: concrete [5], clay bricks [6], tiles [7], aerated concrete [8], wood [9], glass [10], plastics [11], asphalt and bituminous materials [12], soil, thermal insulation materials [13], metals, and gypsum [14]. All these materials can be either recycled or contaminate the secondary materials when improperly sorted. The goal of this work is to present a preliminary study into the use of lightweight computer vision (CV) algorithms for the automatic recognition of selected CDW materials. The correlations between individual features extracted from images of CDW materials can be further used to train different machine-learning models.

2 ALGORITHMS

The purpose of this study was to exploit comprehensive image datasets acquired using drones and develop strategies to distinguish between individual CDW materials using rather a lightweight computer vision (CV)

based algorithms. This section provides an overview of metrics that were used for quantifying the morphology and color distribution in the images. The work deals purely with identifications based on material texture/coloring, identification of CDW within images and its segmentation is out of the scope of this study. All the algorithms were used for the calculation of metrics for relatively small pixel subsets (a square window) in order to save computational time, and memory, and enable future evaluation of materials within nonhomogeneous CDW. Local coordinates (i, j) were introduced for these subsets, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Local coordinates (i, j) for a subset of pixels (right), arbitrarily located within an image (left).

2.1 Mean Intensity Gradient

The mean intensity gradient (δ) was proposed by Pan et al. [15] as an appropriate parameter for the evaluation of stochastic patterns used for digital image correlation (DIC). The principle of DIC is to locate subsets within a sequence of images and calculate their relative position and deformation. For this purpose, these subsets must be unique and contain enough information. The larger the mean gradient is, the more unique subsets can be found within an isotropic nonhomogeneous image. For the evaluation of texture roughness, it is not necessary to investigate the directional components of the gradient and the normalized average is sufficient to evaluate the texture roughness.

2.2 Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's Entropy was proposed by Claude Shannon in 1948 and expresses the average level of uncertainty in a signal, e.g., an image. A curious reader is referred to [16, 17] for the definition; the higher Shannon's entropy value, the higher the uncertainty of the signal/image (randomness).

3 CASE STUDY

The proposed method for automatic recognition of CDW materials is based on selecting a suitable set of parameters that can answer the following question: (1) how grainy (rough) the material is, and (2) what the color composition is, preferably not dependent (or in a limited way) on the scale and resolution of the images. These questions can be answered using different metrics and the goal of the presented case study was to select the most appropriate ones, creating a linear space in which individual materials are represented with clusters. These parameters were calculated for square subsets of pixels (recall Figure 1) that were randomly selected from images of different CDW materials; the study on the convergence of the tested parameters with increasing subset size revealed their minimum size. The presented study shows that some parameters are inadequate or that there is a strong correlation between parameters and therefore these can be replaced one by another. Revealing these relationships maximizes both the accuracy and versatility of the developed method.

The recognition of CDW materials was accomplished using two sets of images: (i) those acquired using a handheld digital single-lens reflex (DSLR) camera Canon EOS 6D and (ii) images cropped from video

frames recorded using a DJI Mavic 2 Pro drone. The first set was used for the development of the algorithms and methods, while the latter was for their validation. In (i), each material was represented by 6 images, in (ii) there were 50 to 120 distinct images representing each material. All the images were taken in the CDW sorting yard of the Moravostav company in Modřice near Brno, Czechia. The company is among the partners in the Decompose project [18].

3.1 Selection of metrics using DSLR images

A few samples of images representing individual CDW materials are presented in Figure 2; gravel and ceramics were, however, represented by more fractions. In total, there were six distinct materials tested: asphalt, ceramics, gravel, sand, soil, and stones. Gravel was represented by seven fractions (0–4, 0–32, 0–64, 4–8, 8–16, 16–32, and 32–64 mm) and crushed ceramics by three (fine, medium, and coarse). The asphalt was in a form of scraped road surface forming rather large flat pieces. The sand was fine, fraction 0–4 mm. The most nonhomogeneous material was the soil, containing clay, stones, fertile dark soils, and even a small portion of organic matter. The stones consisted of small fractions as well as large rocks.

The algorithms (mean intensity gradient, entropy, and color-based metrics) were tested for each image considering several subset sizes (from 10 to 200 px with the increment of 10 px) and each subset size was represented by 10 randomly positioned subsets. For illustration, the analyses for asphalt and coarse (0–32 mm) gravel samples are presented here (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Relationship between the subset size and mean of individual RGB channels for DSLR images of gravel samples.

The texture characteristics (the mean intensity gradient, δ , and the mean entropy, H) both reflected the different roughness of the tested materials; however, the correlation was rather weak, and H was far less sensitive to texture changes than δ . Pearson’s correlation coefficient for these two metrics was low, about 0.5, due to the high sensitivity of H of subset size and consistent values independent of the studied material. For this reason, δ was selected as the more appropriate parameter for the description of the material texture than H . Both parameters exhibited high scatter (standard deviation), justifying the calculation for several subsets per image.

Mean values for each RGB channel (R, G, and B for red, green, and blue, respectively) exhibit a large scatter for asphalt and low for gravel. This can be explained by the high contrast of asphalt samples since blacks are represented by zeros for each RGB channel while whites are formed by the maximum value for each color. That is why it makes sense to normalize each channel with brightness.

3.2 Validation Based on drone images

The attention was focused on different materials of a single fraction to simplify the analysis and interpretation of results. The video frames, captured by a flying drone, were cropped to a 400×400 px-sized window and consequently used for calculation. Examples of these cropped images are provided in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Examples of images representing individual CDW materials during the validation stage (drone images): asphalt, bricks, ceramics, gravel, sand, and stones.

The analysis of these images according to the procedures described in the previous section led to replacing the mean of the absolute value of red channel R_{rel} to its normalization and setting the subset size range to $N \in [80, 180]$ px, while the subset-size increment remained 10 px, each configuration represented by 5 randomly placed subsets. When placing individual subsets for different materials in the $\delta-R_{rel}$ linear space, the

clustering of these materials is packed and individual materials can be clearly distinguished, except for asphalt and stones, calling for the introduction of an additional parameter that has already been computed, the brightness ζ . In the δ - ζ linear space, the clusters representing these two materials do not overlap, but this time bricks and stones could not be recognized. Combining all the parameters to form a 3D δ - R_{rel} - ζ linear space can fix the problem (Figure 4). Here, the clusters for all the studied CDW materials can be easily distinguished, and for any data a probability of matching any of these groups could be easily calculated. This process is to be developed in future research, along with the addition of more dimensions to the linear space of all possible parameters that describe the texture and color distribution within images.

Figure 4. Drone images of the studied CDW materials in the linear space of R_{rel} , ζ , and δ .

4 CONCLUSIONS

The presented study demonstrates that the use of lightweight easily controlled CV-based algorithms can be considered for the automatic recognition of CDW materials. These algorithms are based on the evaluation of the mean intensity gradient, brightness, and relative representation of a color channel, all calculated for relatively small subsets extracted from larger images. The purpose of this study was to demonstrate the capability of this approach and present the results on representative and frequent CDW materials. Using selected features describing the texture of individual CDW materials can be further used for training of machine learning algorithms and provide the reduction of input space from the number of pixels (times the color channels) to a few features. However, further testing on different materials (wood, concrete, glass, plastics, etc.) and combinations of more metrics must be accomplished before considering the method for application in the industry, e.g., for robotic sorting of CDW on conveyor belts used in sorting plants. In geodesy, the method could be efficiently used for drone scanning and photogrammetry. This could be enabled by employing state-of-the-art machine learning tools implemented in libraries such as Scikit-learn (for Python) or Tensor Flow.

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